

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

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**THE WAYS TO REFLECT AFFECTIVE EMOTIONS (ANGER, JOY, HORROR,
ADMIRATION) AND THEIR EXPRESSION IN LITERARY TEXTS**

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